

Prevalence and Risk Factors of *Schistosoma haematobium* among Students of Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Schistosomiasis is a significant neglected tropical disease affecting human health and endemic to tropical countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria. The study aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection in Federal University Birnin Kebbi (FUBK). In this study, 100 urine samples were collected from the university students, which were processed in the laboratory. The samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5mins and the sediments were examined under a light microscope to detect the presence of *Schistosoma haematobium* eggs. The socioeconomic and demographic information of the participants was obtained through simple random sampling and structured questionnaires. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 26, employing a significance level of $p < 0.05$ and a Chi-square test to determine the significant difference between the prevalence and risk factors. Out of the 100 samples analyzed, 52 (52%) belonged to male students, while 48 (48%) belonged to female students. Remarkably, only one male student (1.9%) was found to be infected with *Schistosoma haematobium*, resulting in an overall prevalence of 1% within the study population. However, the data analysis indicated no significant association ($p < 0.05$) between gender and the prevalence of *S. haematobium* in FUBK. The results of this study show that a mere 0.46% of the students had knowledge about Schistosomiasis, while a significant majority of 54% was unaware of schistosomiasis. Furthermore, the study reveals that 19% of the students do not properly wash their hands with soap and water before meals and after using the toilet. Regarding to potential risk factors, 91% of the students are not in contact with open water bodies, and 74% do not consume water from open sources, while 26% are found to be drinking open water sources. In conclusion, the prevalence (1%) of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection within FUBK was very low, which was statistically insignificant. Based on these finding, there are no evidences on the prevalence and burdens of *S. haematobium*. Nevertheless, the study underscores the importance of continuous surveillance, to prevention the occurrence this infection within the university community. It highlights the need for ongoing efforts in education, awareness, and the promotion of proper hygiene practices to effectively prevent the occurrence of schistosomiasis.

Keywords: Attitude, FUBK, Knowledge, Prevalence, *Schistosoma haematobium*, Schistosomiasis.

1.0 Introduction

Schistosomiasis is a prevalent waterborne parasitic disease caused by blood flukes, which is transmitted through contaminated water bodies, with a manifestation of substantial impact on public health and economies, particularly in tropical countries [1]. Approximately 779 million people worldwide are at risk of Schistosome infection, with a population of 207 million

infected individuals, and 97% are particularly reside in Africa [2,3]. Among the five major species known to infect humans, *Schistosoma haematobium*, *S. mansoni*, and *S. japonicum* are the most prevalent species associated with significant public health problem [4]. Additionally, *S. mekongi* and *S. intercalatum* are also found to infect humans but are less prevalent [4, 5]. Some avian schistosomes, such as *S. bovis*

and *S. mattheei* occasionally caused dermatitis or insignificant infections in humans [6].

In Nigeria, urinary schistosomiasis exhibits substantial transmission throughout the country, with high prevalence rates among school-age children [29,3,]. The disease is prevalent in all 36 states of Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory [3]. It is estimated that approximately 101.28 million people in Nigeria are at risk of schistosome infection, with 25.83 million currently infected [8]. The distribution of schistosomiasis varies across different geographic regions, making it crucial to conduct adequate research to obtain a clear epidemiological picture and effectively plan control measures [8]. Schistosomes primarily affect the intestines and liver, except for *Schistosoma haematobium*, which targets the urinary tract [8]. Understanding the biological differences between the various schistosome species, their geographical distribution, and the diseases they cause is essential for developing effective control strategies [9].

Schistosomiasis, caused by the parasitic flatworm *Schistosoma haematobium*, is a neglected tropical disease (NTD) predominantly affecting the urinary tract. It remains a significant public health concern in Nigeria, particularly in the northwestern region where Birnin Kebbi is located [10]. The large population of Federal University Birnin Kebbi (FUBK), will make it a hotspot for transmission of *S. haematobium*. Activities like swimming and water collection from potentially contaminated sources within the Kalgo town increase the students' risk of exposure [11]. Unfortunately, the current prevalence of *S. haematobium* among FUBK students is unknown. The existing literature on *S. haematobium* in Nigeria primarily focuses on rural communities and lacks comprehensive data on the prevalence and risk factors within university settings. Therefore, this study aims to determine the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among students of the Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria, to assess their knowledge and attitudes, and investigate the potential risk factors associated with infection. Such a study can also identify factors associated with *S. haematobium* infections to tailored health education and awareness programs, and design strategic plan for prevention and control. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment can significantly reduce disease progression and complications.

The findings will provides practical skills in shaping the control strategies not only in university community but also in rural and urban areas, thereby contributing to the overall reduction of *S. haematobium* infection in Nigeria [10,11].

Through the investigation of *S. haematobium* prevalence and associated risk factors among FUBK students, this study has the potential to significantly improve the health and well-being of the vulnerable population and contribute to the broader fight against schistosomiasis in Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of study area

Federal University Birnin Kebbi (FUBK) is a university located in Kebbi State, northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It lies between latitude 12.4318°N, and longitude 4.1956° E [12]. The predominant and indigenous people of the state, are, Hausa, Fulani, and Zuru who are predominantly farmers and animal breeders. The vegetation of the state comprises a mixture of grasses and sparse trees, which is atypical characteristic of Sudan Savannah. The climate is mainly dry, occurring between May to October, and the remaining months are wet. The average annual rainfall is 740 mm, while the temperature may be as high as 41°C and as low as 15°C [13].

2.2 Study population, Sample Collection and Processing

A total of 100 University students participated in the study, with 52 males and 48 females, providing mid-stream urine samples for the analysis of *S. haematobium*. The urine samples were collected in sterile containers and promptly transported to the Laboratory Department of Microbiology, Federal University Birnin Kebbi. In the laboratory, 10 ml of each urine sample was transferred to centrifuge test tubes and centrifuged at a speed of 5000 rpm for 5 minutes [14]. The supernatant was discarded by inverting the test tubes, leaving the sediment at the bottom. The sediment was gently mixed by tapping the tube, and then the content was transferred onto a clean, grease-free glass slide using a pipette. A cover slip was carefully placed over the sample [14]. The prepared slide was examined under a light microscope (FMOH/NTBLCP/213/19), utilizing

x10 and x40 objective lenses, to confirm the presence of parasite eggs. The results of the microscopic examination for each sample were recorded [15].

The data on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to schistosomiasis were collected using administered questionnaire. The questionnaire also collected demographic information such as age, gender, socio-economic background, and potential risk factors like hand washing habits, water sanitation practices. Furthermore, the questionnaire inquired about the participants' health conditions, including their infection history and the presence of hematuria (blood in urine). The students were voluntarily participated.

2.3 Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Prior to the commencement of the research, the study received approval from the Ethics Committee of Federal University Birnin Kebbi. Written consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their informed agreement to participate in the study. Throughout the research process, strict adherence was maintained to the guidelines for teaching and research established by the Committee.

3.4 Data analysis

The collected data was entered into Microsoft Excel 2013. Descript statics were used to determine the frequencies and were expressed as percentages. The study used the Chi-square statistical distribution tool (SPSS version 26) to

determine the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection and identify significant associations with potential risk factors.

3.0 Results

Among the 100 urine samples collected, only one sample from the male student was found to be positive, this indicates a low prevalence of *S. haematobium* in Federal University Birnin Kebbi with (Fig. 1). The positive sample was obtained from a male student, accounting for 1.9% of the male participants (Table 1). However, the data analysis indicated no significant association ($p < 0.05$) between gender and the prevalence of *S. haematobium* in Federal University Birnin Kebbi (Table 1). Table 2 revealed the potential risk factors associated with *S. haematobium* in which 20% of students were living in areas with agricultural activities involving exposure to water sources, Socio-economic Factors: Poverty and lack of access to healthcare facilities were reported by 30% of students, significant portion (54%) of students were unaware of the risk of Schistosomiasis (Table 2). The knowledge and attitudes of the students revealed that 46% of the students were aware of Schistosomiasis, while the remaining 54% lacked knowledge about the disease (Table 3). 19% of students reported not washing hands with soap and water before meals or after using the toilet. Furthermore, 74% of the respondents did not drink open water sources, while 26% reported are associated with drinking open water sources. Regarding to the hygiene practices among the students, and 9% had contact with open water sources in their various metropolis from which they also consumed water (Table 3).

Fig. 1: Prevalence of *S. haematobium* among students of Federal University Birnin Kebbi

Table 1: Gender Based Prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among FUBK students

Gender	Total no. of sample (%)	No. of positive samples (%)	Chi-square Analysis
Male	52 (52%)	1 (1.9%)	P-value = 0.334
Female	48 (48%)	0 (0%)	
Total	100 (100%)	1 (1%)	$\chi^2 = 0.932$

Table 2: Potential risk factor of urinary Schistosomiasis among FUBK students

Hand hygiene Practice	Environmental factors	Source of water for drinking	Lack of awareness	Socio-economic factors
Lack of hand washing with soap and water before meals or after using the toilet (19%)	Those leaving in an area of Agricultural activity (20%)	Drinking of water from open source (26%)	Not knowing the risk of Schistosomiasis (54%)	Poverty and lack of access to healthcare facility (30%)

Table 3: Knowledge, Attitude and practice of FUBK Student

Factor	Positive Frequency	Negative Frequency
Knowledge awareness of schistosomiasis	46% are knowledgeable	54% of the students were ignorant
Practice of the student	81% properly wash their hands with soap and water before meals and after using the toilet	19% do not wash their hands with soap and water before meals or after using the toilet
Water contact	91% are not in contact with open water bodies	about 9% are in contact with open water bodies

4.0 Discussion:

The present study investigates the prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among students at Federal University Birnin-Kebbi. The findings revealed a prevalence rate of 1%, ($p < 0.05$) which contrasts with the results of previous studies conducted in [16], [17], and [18], which reported prevalence rates of 41.5% and 24.3% respectively [19]. The prevalence rate of 1% in the present study appears to be relatively low when compared to the findings of similar study conducted by [19]. The variations between the findings in the literature could possibly be due to the geographical locations, aged of the participants, sample size and environmental conditions, which can influence the abundance and distribution of the intermediate host (snails) and the availability of suitable water bodies for parasites transmission [19]. Similarly, the study observed a higher prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among males (1.9%) compared to females (0.0%)

students. However, statistical analysis indicated that the prevalence is insignificant, which aligns with the findings of a previous study [19], [20] and [2]. This suggests that gender alone may not be a determining factor for the prevalence of schistosomiasis, but rather the level of exposure to the contaminated water sources and contact with cercariae (infective larval stage) [5]. Other researchers have also supported the notion that prevalence rates can be influenced by water usage and contact patterns rather than gender alone [19, 22].

The results indicate that only 46% of the participants were aware of the disease, while the remaining 54% lacked an understanding on the public health problems associated with the infections of *S. haematobium*, including transmission mode and the effective prevention measures [4, 23, 24, 25]. Therefore, contributing to the persistence and transmission of

schistosomiasis within Nigerian universities [19, 22].

Several studies conducted in Nigerian Schools have reported similar findings regarding inadequate knowledge about schistosomiasis among students. For instance, a study conducted by Salwa et al. [1] in a Nigerian schools, found that only 74.5% of the participants had heard about schistosomiasis, while the majority lacked proper knowledge about its transmission and prevention [10]. Another study by Hany et al. [25] reported that 92.4% of the students were aware of schistosomiasis, and misconceptions regarding its causes and prevention were prevalent [11]. Study also conducted in Ethiopia by Getaneh et al. 2024 [26] reported 24% of the student had knowledge of Schistosomiasis infection.

The misconceptions identified in the current study, have also been reported by the previous research. Adeoye et al. [1] highlighted that some students believed schistosomiasis are inherited through bloodline [10]. In contrary, Gataneh et al. [26] reported that *Schistosoma* infections could be transmitted by drinking water contaminated with *Schistosoma* eggs or exposure to cold weather [11]. These findings collectively underscore the urgent needs for health education programs in Nigerian universities to address the knowledge gaps and misconceptions of schistosomiasis. In order to effectively control the transmission of schistosomiasis in Nigeria Schools, Ekpo et al. [20] emphasized on the necessity for collaboration between healthcare professionals, education stakeholders, and community leaders to implement sustainable control measures [3]. Likewise, Bello et al [27] highlighted the role of community engagement and participation in achieving schistosomiasis control in Nigerian communities [27].

5.0 Conclusion

This study has shed light on the prevalence and risk factors associated with *Schistosoma haematobium* among students of Federal University Birnin Kebbi. Through our discussions, we have identified a significant knowledge gap and misconceptions surrounding schistosomiasis within this population, reflecting some findings from previous research.

To address these gaps and misconceptions effectively, future interventions must be tailored to the specific cultural context and needs of

Nigerian university students. It is imperative that these interventions focus on enhancing knowledge about the signs, symptoms, transmission, and prevention of schistosomiasis.

By incorporating cultural considerations and actively engaging with the target population, interventions can promote accurate understanding of schistosomiasis and encourage behavior change towards preventive practices. Collaboration between healthcare professionals, educational institutions, community leaders, and students themselves will be essential for the successful implementation of these tailored interventions.

Ultimately, by bridging the knowledge gap and addressing misconceptions, we can work towards sustainable control of schistosomiasis among university students in Birnin Kebbi and Nigeria, ensuring better health outcomes for this vulnerable population.

6.0 Author's contribution:

MBD, ASK, GN, AMM, RDS and CLG conceived the study and participated in its design and coordination. MBD, ASK and CLG performed sample collection and analysis. MBD, ASK, GN, AMM, RDS and CLG analyzed the results. MBD and ASK drafted the manuscript.

7.0 Conflict of interest:

All authors have no competing interests.

8.0 Acknowledgements:

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